

WAYS TO TRANSCRIBE THE REPERTOIRE OF EPIC PERFORMANCES

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Recording the repertoire of doston performances can be done in different ways, depending on the desired result. Which of the methods of recording doston melodies is used depends on the goals of the recording and what information is needed for preservation. Each of the methods of preserving melodies can be used to preserve different aspects of the

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work and allows for use in different situations. It should be remembered that in order to preserve the most complete and clear rhythm and melody of the work, it is effective to use a combination of several recording methods. Doston performers can use different methods of recording their repertoire, depending on their preferences, available resources and technical capabilities. One of the most widespread methods is recording on an audio track. Next in importance is the creation of an audio or video of the performance.

Recording onto a sound track can be done using portable recording equipment such as a voice recorder or digital tape recorder, or professional equipment such as a multi-channel mixing console and digital audio interface. During a performance, performers may use microphones to record various sounds and vocals, as well as additional equipment to control volume and sound settings. Doston performers may also use sheet music to record their repertoire. Sheet music can be written by hand on paper or used in electronic programs to create musical notations. Sheet music shows melodies, chords, lyrics, and other details of the work.

Additional methods for recording the repertoire of doston performances include:

Audio recording: recording sound into audio devices such as microphones, tape recorders, and other audio devices. This method allows you to save the sound of the performance and save it in an audio file format. Depending on the

recording goals, this method can be implemented using professional studio recordings or portable audio devices such as smartphones;

Video recording: recording a video using a camcorder, smartphone, or other device to preserve not only the sound, but also the visual component. This method is very effective if the dance or choreographic elements of the epic are recorded, and if it is also appropriate to preserve the rhythms of the performances and the original stage atmosphere;

Transcription: the process of writing the words in text form, translating the work into musical notation in order to preserve the musical part of the poem. This allows the musical composition of the work to be preserved and used for rehearsal or for the development of musical publications;

Visual notation: photographs or sketches depicting stage images, performers' outfits, costumes, sets, and other elements of the poem;

Text writing: the writing of the text of the work in written form. It is important to preserve the content and structure of the work and use it for later analysis or study;

Combined methods: a combination of different recording methods, such as recording audio and video at the same time, to preserve sound and visual elements.

Recording musical parts: recording individual parts of the performances in a musical work. This is useful for further analysis or use of individual musical parts in other works;

Recording rhythmic and melodic patterns: Recording the rhythmic and melodic patterns used in a doston allows for later analysis and research;

Recording oral utterances: Recording oral utterances used in a doston allows for later study and analysis;

Ethnographic writing: A form of writing used in ethnographic research that captures all aspects of a work, including music, lyrics, poems, settings, and other elements;

Video or audio recording: Modern technology makes it easy to record video or audio recordings of epic performances. This is a useful way to preserve live performances and to analyze and study works;

Descriptive writing: recording a description of a work that includes music, lyrics, costumes, and other aspects. This is useful for creating catalogs of works or for preserving work information for future research;

Gathering information from participants: Participants in a doston can be an important source of information about the work. Their stories and memories

help us understand the traditions of performing the doston and the meaning of the work. Ethnographic notes: This method is used to record in detail cultural traditions and practices, including music and lyrics. This method involves recording in video, audio, text, and other formats, as well as interviewing participants and observing practices and ceremonies;

*Editing and compilation*¹: After recording a work and its various aspects, the recordings can be edited and compiled to create a complete and accurate record of the work. This includes cutting, highlighting, and reworking audio and video to create a balanced and understandable record;

Online recordings: There are now online resources that allow recording and storing works and providing access to existing recordings. These can meet the needs of preserving and studying works, as well as sharing information with other participants;

Using artificial intelligence technologies: Artificial intelligence technologies can be used to automatically transcribe audio and video recordings and create musical pieces from audio recordings. This can simplify and speed up the process of recording epic works;

Creating musical notation: This method involves creating musical notation for musical works. It can be used to store, distribute, and study works, facilitate performance, and create arrangements.

Multimedia recording: This is a recording method that combines multiple recording formats, such as video, audio, text, images, and others. It has the advantages of storing and transmitting information about epic works in a more complete and understandable way;

Graphic notation method: This is a method that uses graphic symbols and diagrams to record musical works instead of traditional musical notation. This method is especially used to record music that cannot be recorded using traditional notation;

Folktale recording method: This method involves recording epic works from folktales, which have passed down their knowledge and skills from generation to generation. This allows for the preservation of unique works and traditions that may otherwise be lost over time;

Documentary recording: Documentary film is a useful way to record and preserve epic works, as it has a visual component. The film may also include interviews with performers and experts to give the works more context;

¹ **Compilation** - A work created based on the research and works of others, without any explanation, but by assimilation.

Real-time recording method: This method is used to record works during live performances. It is convenient for preserving and learning different performance styles, as well as evaluating the audience's relationship to the work;

Co-creation: Instead of recording a work using an existing method, the work can be created together with performers and other participants. This helps to preserve the traditions and methods of creating works, as well as create a more unique and personal recording.

Each of the above methods of notation and preservation of melodies has its own advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of a particular method depends on the purpose of using it. For example, if recording the musical parts of a doston is important for subsequent analysis of the musical melody, the transcription method may be preferable for studying the doston language. In any case, the use of several recording methods allows you to preserve the most complete representation of the work - cultural heritage - and also to promote cultural diversity. In some cases, doston performers can record their performances on video, that is, on a video camera or smartphone, for later use. Video recording, along with the audio track, also takes into account the visual aspect of the performance. This provides ample opportunity to capture the unique movements of the performer, the audience's reactions, and other details of the performance.

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